

AI as a Service for Intelligent Mobile Networks: Extending Network Data Analytics Functions

Carlos Barroso-Fernández, Adam Zahir, Pablo Picazo-Martínez, *Student Member, IEEE*, Antonio de la Oliva, *Senior Member, IEEE*, and Carlos J. Bernardos

Abstract—The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into 5G networks has the potential to significantly enhance network resilience, adaptability, and service delivery. This work presents the design and implementation of an Artificial Intelligence as a Service (AIaaS) platform deployed within the 5G Core, enabling both network functions and end-user equipment (UEs) to access AI capabilities in a scalable, low-latency, and energy-efficient manner. Unlike cloud-based AI services or on-device inference, the proposed platform leverages the proximity and flexibility of the 5G network to deliver advanced AI models without overburdening the user device or incurring high transmission delays. The architecture is composed of distributed AI workers – partially reusing the standardized Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) – and a centralized control layer responsible for service orchestration and resource management. The solution is designed to support both internal (i.e., other application functions) and external consumers, and is adaptable to centralized or edge deployments. A Proof-of-Concept (PoC) implementation was developed using the SLICES-Madrid research infrastructure to validate the approach, demonstrating the feasibility of AIaaS within realistic 5G environments. The results underline the potential of AIaaS as a flexible enabler for intelligent network functions and AI-powered services across a wide range of verticals.

Index Terms—6G, AIaaS, Edge intelligence, Service orchestration, OAI, SLICES infrastructure.

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence as a Service (AIaaS) is an emerging paradigm in which third-party providers host and operate Artificial Intelligence (AI) infrastructure, delivering advanced AI services to users and applications via on-demand application programming interfaces (APIs), without the need to manage the underlying systems [1], [2]. Unlike conventional deployments, where AI is either embedded into the User Equipment (UE) or hosted in centralized cloud data centers, 5G-integrated AIaaS offers a unique middle ground. By positioning AI closer to the edge – within or alongside the 5th Generation (5G) network, the system reduces both latency and energy consumption. On one hand, it offloads the computational burden from UEs, enabling lightweight devices to access advanced models. On the other hand, it delivers faster inference than cloud-hosted alternatives, enabling support for latency-sensitive use cases. Moreover, it offers complete control of the whole workflow. This can be a key advantage against other AIaaS deployments when the use case imposes strict privacy constraints, due to not relying on third parties.

The authors are with the Department of Telematics Engineering, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid: {cbarroso, azahir, papicazo}@pa.uc3m.es, {aoliva, cjb}@it.uc3m.es

Fig. 1: Example of AIaaS integrated within 5G network, performing image recognition for visually impaired people.

We identify several use cases that benefit from 5G-integrated AIaaS. One key advantage is accessing to large-scale AI models, which typically require large amounts of data and can only be executed on dedicated servers, for solving time-sensitive and data-intensive tasks. This enables, for example, increased sensing resolution for integrated communication and sensing (ISAC), accurate image detection, or high-quality answers [2]. Moreover, devices with low computational resources or battery-constrained can leverage the platform to solve their tasks using AI models, without exhausting resources or draining the battery – for example, mobile robots in emergency missions [3].

To illustrate the potential impact of this paradigm, let's consider a visually impaired person wearing smart glasses (see Fig. 1). The glasses send images of the surrounding environment in real time to the AIaaS platform in the 5G network, which processes them using deep learning models and returns an audio description to the user within milliseconds. This interaction requires both high computational power and ultra-low latency, requirements that cannot be met by local processing on wearable devices or by remote cloud inference. AIaaS deployed within the 5G network offers an optimal solution, combining responsiveness with the ability to execute sophisticated models.

Motivated by this vision, the objective of our work is to design, implement, and evaluate a functional AIaaS platform that is natively integrated into a 5G network. To that end, we present a real-world testbed that demonstrates how AI services can be delivered to both internal network functions and external consumers, including UEs. Our platform is built upon standard 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) components,

such as the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF), and introduces novel elements like a service orchestration controller to dynamically manage AI workloads. The proposed architecture is validated through a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) deployment using the SLICES [4] research infrastructure, offering insights into its feasibility, energy efficiency, and performance. This work contributes a step forward in bringing intelligent, network-embedded AI services closer to reality.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. First, Sec. II presents the relevant 3GPP architecture and concludes with a literature analysis. Next, Sec. III details our AIaaS framework, Sec. IV presents the PoC, and Sec. V analyzes the obtained results. Last, Sec. VI highlights the takeaway message of the work, and Sec. VII concludes the article.

II. BACKGROUND

To realize the vision of AIaaS within 5G, both architectural support and standardization efforts are essential. The 3GPP has taken initial steps toward enabling AI-driven network intelligence, and various research initiatives have explored advanced concepts and implementations that further validate the feasibility and impact of deploying AIaaS within the telecom domain for future 6th Generation (6G) networks.

A. SDOs enablers

The 5G Core leverages a service-based architecture designed to support diverse use cases, including enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communications (URLLC), and massive machine-type communications (mMTC). Unlike previous generations, the core of 5G is modular, cloud-native, and highly flexible, enabling dynamic deployment and scaling of network functions. The separation of control and user planes enables independent scaling and placement of core functions, for example, User Plane Functions (UPFs) can be deployed closer to the Radio Access Network (RAN) to reduce latency for time-sensitive applications [5].

The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is a component introduced in the 5G Core to enable data-driven network intelligence. As specified in 3GPP TS 23.288 [6], the NWDAF is responsible for collecting, analyzing, and distributing analytics information to other network functions and consumers, thereby supporting optimized network operation and service provisioning. NWDAF aggregates data from various sources, including other network functions, and applies analytics models to derive insights such as traffic patterns, network load, abnormal behavior detection, or service experience. Network functions can consume analytics from NWDAF to guide their decisions. For example, the Session Management Function (SMF) might use load forecasts to perform traffic steering, while the Policy Control Function (PCF) could use user behavior predictions to adjust policy rules dynamically. The NWDAF enables AI and Machine Learning (ML) integration into the 5G Core, particularly by serving as a conduit between raw data and intelligent decision-making systems.

B. Other works on AIaaS

Several research initiatives are currently working toward the definition of AIaaS. Among them, the Hexa-X-II project¹, part of the 6G Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), plays a prominent role.

Hexa-X-II aimed to define the overall architecture and technologies for future mobile networks. A key focus of the project is the integration of AI throughout the network, under the concept of "Connecting Intelligence". The project envisions AIaaS as a distributed service layer embedded across the network. This is supported by an AI-native, service-oriented architecture featuring intelligent orchestration and zero-touch automation. However, unlike Hexa-X-II, which focuses on high-level architectural design and long-term 6G vision, our work presents a concrete, fully implemented AIaaS framework deployed in an operational 5G network.

Thanks to these initiatives, researchers have started to work around this concept. For instance, [7] presents a platform to exchange ML models among NWDAF instances; [8] proposes an evolved NWDAF framework to further empower the core network with AI capabilities; and [9] explores the possibility of integrating AIaaS within the RAN to solve slicing problems, but does not specifically demonstrate or describe how the AI service is deployed.

Apart from integrating AIaaS within a 5G network, there are other authors that followed a similar approach, but moving the platform from the cloud to the edge [2]. In [10], the authors propose an edge-based AIaaS architecture that dynamically adjusts model and data quality to optimize energy and delay performance. Similarly, [11] presents an algorithm to decide where to perform the inference of a Large Language Model based on the requirements.

While these studies mark progress toward the integration of AI into next-generation networks, they remain largely at the architectural or conceptual level, lacking a complete AIaaS implementation or validation in an operational 5G environment. To fill this gap, our work introduces a functional AIaaS framework integrated into the 5G Core (presented in the next section), supported by a PoC implementation and experimental validation in a real-world testbed.

III. MICROSERVICE-BASED AIAAS FRAMEWORK

This section presents our novel AIaaS-powered framework for extending the NWDAF, outlining first its architectural design and key functionalities (Sec. III-A) and then its operational workflow (Sec. III-B).

A. System Architecture

The system architecture of the proposed framework is illustrated in Fig. 2. It builds on the microservice-based design of NWDAF introduced in previous studies [12] and incorporates a novel integration with an AIaaS platform. This integration enables the execution of a broad range of AI services that address both network-level analytics and higher-layer application tasks, and supports the flexible, dynamic

¹<https://hexa-x-ii.eu>

Fig. 2: AIaaS-powered microservice architecture extending NWDAF capabilities.

deployment of service-specific AI workers across the compute continuum to enhance automation and operational intelligence.

The architecture is organized into two main categories of functional components: *i*) logically centralized control functions, and *ii*) distributed AI functions that are dynamically instantiated on demand as NWDAF-based AIaaS workers, each tailored to a specific AI service.

AIaaS control layer. This layer handles global coordination, orchestration, and lifecycle management of AI services. It comprises three main components, each designed following microservice principles to ensure modularity, scalability, and interoperability.

First, the *AIaaS API Gateway* serves as the main entry point to the system, exposing a unified high-level API to both internal (e.g., core network functions) and external (e.g., vertical tenants, application developers) consumers. It supports: *i*) on-demand provisioning of AI services, *ii*) interaction with deployed services by querying analytics outputs or subscribing to real-time event notifications, and *iii*) uploading of new ML models for future use.

Second, the *ML Repository* manages the collection of trained ML models available to the system. It supports version control, metadata tracking, and tagging based on performance or deployment constraints (e.g., CPU vs. GPU models), ensuring efficient and reusable model deployment.

Third, the *AIaaS Orchestrator* is responsible for the orchestration, configuration, and lifecycle management of AIaaS workers. Upon receiving an AI service request, it interprets the intended task (e.g., traffic prediction, optimization, image classification), selects the most appropriate model from the ML Repository, and provisions an AIaaS worker instance accordingly. Deployment decisions take into account task-specific constraints such as communication latency, bandwidth, and available computational resources. For ongoing services, when

a consumer queries analytics results, the AIaaS Orchestrator routes the request to the corresponding AIaaS worker, which responds via its exposure layer using the Northbound Interface (NBI).

AIaaS worker layer. Each AIaaS worker is a lightweight, task-specific execution unit instantiated dynamically in response to a consumer request. It is provisioned with the selected ML model, inference engine, and necessary interfaces for consuming telemetry data and exposing analytics results. Optionally, a local database can also be included when historical information is required (e.g., in trend analysis or predictive modeling tasks).

The proposed AIaaS framework enhances the capabilities of traditional NWDAF deployments by extending analytics operations beyond the native scope of 5G network functions. Currently, 3GPP defines the NWDAF to support networking tasks for other network functions [6], leveraging data analytics and AI models. However, its working area is limited to only serving network functions through the N23 interface or SBA. We envision an extended functionality for the NWDAF, enabling it not only to interact with the core but also to offer its services to a broader range of clients, including direct access to RAN nodes' information. Consequently, its capabilities are abstracted to support any type of data analytics or AI model. To achieve this, we introduce two complementary interfaces, *Ne* and *Ne-E*, as illustrated in the PoC testbed setup (Fig. 4). They provide the same set of services defined for the N23 interface, while extending their exposure to a wider range of consumers beyond the 5G Core. In this way, the NWDAF's analytical and AI capabilities can be seamlessly leveraged by the RAN or indirectly by UEs.

Note that we decided to reuse NWDAF and extend its functionality beyond the 3GPP scope because defining a new network function will overlap in functionality to the

NWDAF. This approach is already followed in the literature, for example, the author from [13] considers NWDAF as a potential element to provide sensing within 6G networks, but they highlight the need to broaden its current scope. This trend is also adopted by 3GPP working groups, which are continuously evolving this network function – see the activities of 3GPP SA Working Group 5².

In the proposed framework, AIaaS workers are capable of collecting and processing data from diverse sources – from core network functions to UEs – thus enabling a broader range of AI-driven services. This functionality is realized through the use of the southbound interface (SBI) to obtain analytical metrics and the northbound interface (NBI) to deliver processed insights to consumers.

Moreover, the modular deployment strategy minimizes overhead and enables scalable, distributed analytics across heterogeneous network domains, including RAN, transport, edge, and core, supporting the vision of a fully integrated compute continuum with intelligent, adaptive, and efficient network operations.

B. Framework operation

Fig. 3 illustrates the end-to-end workflow for fulfilling an AI service request within the proposed AIaaS platform. The process begins when an AIaaS consumer – represented by a UE in the example – initiates a service request through the AIaaS API Gateway (step 1). This request specifies the type of AI service to be provisioned (e.g., image classification, object detection, or another ML-based task), along with the associated performance requirements (e.g., latency, bandwidth, compute resources).

Upon receiving the request, the AIaaS API Gateway forwards it to the AIaaS Orchestrator, which coordinates the provisioning process (step 2). The AIaaS Orchestrator identifies the most suitable ML model from the ML Repository (step 3) and determines the optimal deployment location for the AIaaS worker based on the service type, performance constraints, and available resources. For example, if the service requires real-time operation, the orchestrator aims to deploy the worker on a computational node positioned as close as possible to the UE to minimize latency. This decision can be supported by infrastructure information from the service provider (e.g., mobile network operator, cloud/edge provider). Once the model and deployment location are selected, the AIaaS Orchestrator generates a deployment descriptor and triggers the instantiation of the worker (steps 4 and 5) on the virtual infrastructure. The deployed worker includes the selected model, inference engine, relevant data interfaces, and (optionally) a local database if historical data is required.

After deployment, the AIaaS Orchestrator returns the worker instance details (e.g., service endpoints, capabilities) to the UE via the API Gateway (step 6). At this point, the UE can upload input data (e.g., an image from an onboard sensor) directly to the worker for processing (step 7). The worker performs the inference task and returns the result to the UE upon completion (steps 8 and 9).

Fig. 3: AIaaS service provisioning workflow (example: image detection request from an UE).

This flow demonstrates the platform’s capability to dynamically provision and manage AI resources on demand, while maintaining low-latency execution and efficient utilization of the available compute infrastructure. It also highlights the modular nature of the system, in which AI services are composed of loosely coupled components that communicate through well-defined APIs.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PROOF-OF-CONCEPT

To validate the feasibility and effectiveness of deploying AIaaS within a real 5G network environment, we developed a dedicated PoC implementation. Since the orchestration of the deployment does not interfere with the service, we left its validation out of this PoC, and planned for future work. The deployment was conducted on the SLICES research infrastructure.

A. SLICES

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) initiative is a strategic instrument for ensuring open, competitive access to top-tier research infrastructures. Scientific Large-scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies (SLICES) [4] is the first ESFRI project dedicated to advancing research in Information and Communication Technologies, and has been part of the ESFRI Roadmap since 2021.

SLICES-Madrid³ features an open-source, fully configurable end-to-end 5G testbed. It supports multiple core network implementations, including Open5GS, OAI-5GC, and free5GC, available to external researchers. For radio access, it integrates Software Radio Systems and OpenAirInterface5G, supporting various cell setups and enabling next Generation Node B (gNB) deployment across multiple frequency bands and numerologies. As UE, users can connect through industrial 5G HATs (Hardware Attached on Top), commercial smartphones, or an emulator, with support for up to 56 UEs.

²<https://www.3gpp.org/3gpp-groups/service-system-aspects-sa/sa-wg5>

³<https://www.slices-madrid.eu/blueprint-5g-research-infrastructure>

Fig. 4: Experimental testbed.

B. Bringing AI capabilities to the RAN Edge

Leveraging the open-source and highly configurable nature of the SLICES-Madrid platform, we deployed an AIaaS worker on top of an OpenAirInterface (OAI)-based network. The worker extends a modular NWDAF implementation, deployed as a set of containers that communicate directly with the OAI control and user plane to enable real-time data collection and inference. Although the 3GPP standard defines NWDAF primarily as a core network function, we extend its functionality beyond this traditional scope. Additionally, we enable its deployment at both the edge and extreme edge of the network. In this context, we implement an AI-enabled system where an AIaaS worker consumes user data to deliver tailored inference services to specific UEs.

In our PoC, an AIaaS worker is deployed at the extreme edge, near the UE and radio units, to minimize latency and enable real-time AI processing. Since the standard NWDAF framework is primarily designed for centralized analytics within the core, our approach introduces additional interfaces and data flows that allow AIaaS worker instances to operate efficiently at the edge and extreme edge. These enhancements enable secure ingestion of selected UE data, inter-operation with distributed compute resources, and fast execution of AI models near the data source.

By repositioning AIaaS worker functionality closer to the data source, our system significantly reduces inference latency and traffic load, enabling distributed, context-aware intelligence within the 5G network. Our setup (for the use case of image recognition) supports AIaaS through the execution of a YOLOv8 [14] object detection model, enabling rapid environmental description for use cases such as assistance for visually impaired individuals.

C. Implementation hardware and software

Our PoC architecture, illustrated in Fig. 4, was deployed using a combination of commercial and research-grade hardware components to build a fully functional 5G testbed that supports both end-to-end connectivity and AI services⁴.

5G Core: The core network, based on OAI as mentioned earlier, was deployed using Docker containers on a general-purpose server equipped with an Intel Xeon Silver 4314 @ 3.4 GHz CPU and 32 GB RAM. This server hosts all control plane functions required for the 5G workflow and enables real traffic to reach the UE. To minimize user-plane latency, the UPF was placed on the same server as the RAN, following the approach recommended in [5].

Radio Access Network (RAN): The RAN was implemented using a USRP N310 software-defined radio (SDR), connected via a 10 Gbps SFP+ link to a server featuring an AMD Ryzen 9 7900 (12-core @ 3.7 GHz) CPU and 32 GB RAM. A 100 MHz bandwidth 5G cell was deployed in band N78 using OAI⁵.

AIaaS worker: The AI inference workload was offloaded to an AIaaS worker, implemented as a modular NWDAF-based container. This worker was deployed on the same machine as the RAN and UPF, which serves as the edge node for signal processing and AI execution.

User Equipment (UE): A Samsung A33 commercial smartphone was used as the UE, providing connectivity to the 5G network and acting as a consumer of AI services. Its SIM card was manually configured to register with the private core network, enabling user identification as an AIaaS client and allowing the application of potential Quality-of-Service (QoS) policies.

⁴Link to the implementation will be added upon acceptance of the manuscript.

⁵<https://openairinterface.org>

We evaluated our AIaaS platform by executing an image recognition task using the YOLOv8 model [14] under three distinct deployment scenarios:

Local execution. The model runs directly on the UE. However, since the Samsung A33 smartphone does not support native model execution in the Android environment, we connected a mini-PC to the UE via USB 3.1 to serve as an external processing unit. The mini-PC features an Intel Core i5-3610ME CPU, 4 GB RAM, and runs Ubuntu 22.04 as the operating system, providing a hardware profile comparable to mid-range smartphones.

5G AIaaS (proposed approach). The model is deployed on an AIaaS worker node located at the edge of the 5G network, enabling low-latency inference near the UE.

Cloud execution. The model is deployed in a remote cloud environment accessed over the Internet. This scenario represents the case where the AIaaS is instantiated in the cloud. Hence, the UE communicates with the cloud via the 5G network to satisfy the service. The cloud node runs on an Intel Xeon CPU and NVIDIA Tesla T4 GPU, hosted via Google Colab⁶.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We evaluated the performance of the proposed framework in terms of latency and energy consumption across the three deployment scenarios described in previous section: local execution on the UE, and remote execution via edge-based and cloud-based AIaaS. To ensure a fair comparison, we used the first eight images from the COCO train 2017 dataset⁷, processed with the nano variant of YOLOv8 [14] – the only version lightweight enough to run on the UE. Each image was analyzed twenty times by the model under each experimental scenario. For the edge and cloud AIaaS scenarios, images are first uploaded to the inference node, and the results are then downloaded, emulating a realistic workflow where image data originates at the UE.

Fig. 5 shows the average execution time, broken down into upload, inference, and download phases, for processing an image. Despite the communication overhead, the 5G-integrated AIaaS achieves similar – or slightly better – latency than local execution. This difference can be potentially enlarged by optimizing any of the parts, e.g., introducing a GPU-enabled server at the edge to process the model. In contrast, the cloud setup takes the highest total latency, but its inference time is the shortest due to dedicated GPU acceleration. Note that cloud transmission delays are theoretical estimations; a real-world pipeline may suffer from higher delays due to the unpredictability of the network.

Fig. 6 presents a comparison of the average energy consumption during inference, broken down by hardware component (radio transmission, GPU, RAM, CPU) when processing a single image. Measurements were collected using the Codecarbon⁸ tool, which monitors the resource consumption of a given process or task within a machine. It is important to note,

Fig. 5: Comparison of average latency across upload, inference, and download phases for processing a single image using different deployment options.

Fig. 6: Comparison of average energy consumption by hardware resource (radio transmission, GPU, RAM, CPU) during inference for processing a single image using different deployment options.

however, that this tool does not currently monitor the energy consumption of the network interface card (NIC). To compare this expenditure, we theoretically obtain the marginal energy consumed by sending and receiving an image of 60 kB through our radio channel, which can be despised in absolute terms as we can see in Fig. 6. Looking at the figure, a significant benefit of the AIaaS option is evident: by offloading computation, it consumes substantially less energy. Specifically, the AIaaS reduces local energy consumption by more than 50%, with the CPU being the primary source of savings. Note that, in both remote inference scenarios, consumption is measured on the server and the UE. Results show that UE contributes negligibly to the overall consumption in these setups. Therefore, the end device’s savings correspond to its expenditure in the Local case. Comparing 5G-integrated AIaaS against cloud cases, the latter consumes approximately half. Cloud servers, unlike edge servers, are typically deployed for computing tasks and own better hardware, even hardware accelerators such as GPUs – in our deployment, the cloud server is the only one using it. Edge servers, on the other hand, are specialized in network tasks. In addition, these results cannot be compared as absolute values, as they are measured in different platforms, but they give us insights of its behavior.

It is worth noting, however, that offloading inference to the cloud is not suitable for all contexts. Certain use cases, such as healthcare monitoring, assisted living (including the presented assistance for visually impaired individuals), or industrial safety, impose strict privacy constraints. In such cases, running the model inside a controlled environment becomes essential to ensure data confidentiality, even if it implies higher energy consumption. This trade-off highlights

⁶<https://colab.research.google.com>

⁷<https://cocodataset.org/#home>

⁸<https://codecarbon.io>

the importance of adaptable deployment strategies, where the choice between local, edge, or cloud execution depends not only on energy efficiency or latency, but also on privacy constraints and regulatory compliance.

Therefore, our results demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed AIaaS framework, enabling advanced AI capabilities at competent times without sacrificing UE performance or battery life.

VI. LESSONS LEARNED & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Throughout the development and evaluation of our AIaaS platform, several key insights have emerged. First, centralizing AI processing within the 5G Core reduces the computational and energy burden on the end device while enabling the execution of more sophisticated AI models that would otherwise be infeasible on resource-constrained UEs, e.g., smart glasses. This limitation became evident during the development of our PoC, where an initial attempt to use a Raspberry Pi as the UE failed due to its insufficient processing capacity.

In comparison to conventional cloud-based AIaaS deployments, our solution also offers lower and controlled latency, making it well-suited for time-sensitive services. This is a critical advantage in domains such as autonomous driving, virtual or augmented reality, and industrial automation, where milliseconds matter. An additional advantage is that user data remains in the telecom network domain, contrary to the cloud approach, so the end user only needs to rely its privacy concerns on its provider, avoiding third parties. However, one notable limitation we encountered relates to hardware availability in current 5G Core deployments, specifically, the general lack of GPU resources [15], which limits the scalability until they become more common in telecom infrastructure.

Our work demonstrates the feasibility of integrating AIaaS into 5G networks, offering flexible and energy-efficient AI capabilities across all network elements, from core functions to UEs. This concept aligns with the design principles of next-generation networks, particularly 6G, which is envisioned as an AI-native platform delivering services that extend beyond traditional communication paradigms. We expect this work represents a meaningful step toward realizing the 6G vision and contribute to shaping future 3GPP releases.

Looking ahead, there are several promising directions for future work. First, we plan to deploy our solution in scenarios involving multiple UEs and 5G core instances, analyzing the system scalability, resource utilization, and orchestration strategies. Another area for improvement is the definition of open, vendor-neutral APIs, which would simplify integration with third-party network functions and could pave the way toward broader adoption.

VII. CONCLUSION

This work presents a framework for integrating AIaaS into 5G network architecture. It leverages the NWDAF functionality – a network function capable of data analytics – to provide AI services to the UE. To validate the proposed framework, a Proof-of-Concept implementation was deployed leveraging the SLICES infrastructure. Experimental results demonstrate

its feasibility, showing comparable, or even better, response times than fully-local deployments, saving battery life of the UE.

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Carlos Barroso-Fernández got his M.Sc. in 2022 and is a Ph.D. student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M).

Adam Zahir got his M.Sc. in 2024 and is a Ph.D. student at UC3M.

Pablo Picazo-Martínez got his M.Sc. in 2022 and is a Ph.D. student at UC3M.

Antonio de la Oliva got his M.Sc. in 2004 and his Ph.D. in 2008, and he is an associate professor at UC3M.

Carlos J. Bernardos got his M.Sc. in 2003 and his Ph.D. in 2006, and he is a Professor at UC3M.